

of the compound. The compound gave red colour on treatment with concentrated sulphuric acid, showing the presence of at least one methoxyl group in any α -position⁶. The product obtained after the sulphuric acid treatment was found to be Physcion (Amaz 290 and 436 nm, m.p. 207°). Thus of the two methoxyl groups present in the aglycone, one is at β -position and the other is at α -position.

The compound on oxidation gave 3 : 5 dimethoxy phthalic acid as one of the products which places the two methoxyl groups in position 6 and 8. Thus the aglycone is 1-hydroxy-6,8-dimethoxy-3-methyl anthraquinone.

The glycoside was non reducing and when subjected to periodate oxidation it consumed 3 moles of periodate per mole of the glycoside and one mole of formic acid was liberated. Thus the two sugars are linked as a bioside unit. Partial hydrolysis liberated glucose first showing that rhamnose was linked to the aglycone. The glycoside was not hydrolysed by taka-diastase but was completely hydrolysed by emulsion thereby showing the linkages to be β . The periodate oxidation also proved that the glucose and rhamnose are present as a 1 : 4 bioside. Since there is only one hydroxyl group in the aglycone at position-1, the sugar moiety must be linked at position-1. This has also been confirmed by UV spectral study^{4,5}.

Thus the glycoside is 6,8-dimethoxy 3-methyl anthraquinone-1,-O- β -rhamnosyl glucopyranoside.

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2'-Hydroxy-4-Methoxy-S⁺-Methylchalkone Oxime (HMMCO) as indicator for the Direct NTA Titration of Iron(III)

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THE substances reported in literature as indicators for the direct titration of ferric ions with nitrotri-acetic acid (NTA) are chromozurol-S⁺, pyrocatechol violet², N-benzoyl-N-phenyl-hydroxylamine³ and phenolic aldoximes⁴. The present article reports the use of 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalkone oxime⁵⁻⁸ (HMMCO) as an indicator for the direct NTA titration of iron (III).

Experimental

Reagents: A stock solution of ferric nitrate (0.1M) was prepared in 0.1N hydrochloric acid and was standardized with Na₂EDTA using varianine blue as an indicator at pH 2.4. A solution of NTA (0.025M) was prepared by dissolving required quantity of NTA in sodium bi-carbonate solution. 1.0% solution of 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalkone oxime (HMMCO) was prepared in ethyl alcohol.

Titration procedure: Required amount of Fe(III) was taken in conical flask and it was diluted to desired volume. Then required number of drops of HMMCO solution were added to the solution and it was titrated against NTA solution from microburette. The equivalence point was detected by knowing the colour change from blue to yellow.

Results and Discussion

The effective pH range for titration of Fe(III) with NTA is 1.4 to 1.6. End point is also sharp. The results obtained show that in the determination of Fe(III) in small quantity, minimum amount of water to be added was 10 ml. However, large excess of water did not affect the results. The present method is applicable for the determination of Fe(III) in the concentration range of 4.0 to 16.0 mgs in 10.0 ml of water with $\pm 1.0\%$ error. It was observed that addition of four drops of 1% indicator solution gave satisfactory results.

The titrations of synthetic solutions were carried out at pH 1.6. At 2.8 mg concentration of iron 100 times excess of Na⁺, K⁺, NH₄⁺, Cl⁻, Br⁻, SO₄²⁻, 50 times excess of UO₂²⁺, 5 times excess of Cd²⁺, Zn²⁺, Al³⁺ and Mg²⁺ could be tolerated. Cu²⁺, Cr³⁺, Th⁴⁺ and anions forming stable complex with iron such as phosphates, vanadates, molybdates and tungstates interfered at all levels.

Ten titrations were performed with same amount of Fe(III) at pH 1.6 with four drops of indicator solution. The values of relative and standard deviations were found to be 0.80% and 0.36% respectively

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Quantitative Studies on the Water Decomposition Product of Ethereal Blue perchromate Prepared with 5-Sulphosalicylic acid : A Colorimetric Determination*

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THOUGH several workers¹⁻⁷ have tried to establish the presence of Cr(III) along with Cr(VI) in various decomposition products of ethereal blue perchromate, no work is on record for colorimetric determination of chromium present in the water decomposition product using *s*-diphenylcarbazide as a sensitive complexing agent.⁸

Hence to ascertain the composition of the water decomposition product, $(\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}\text{Su})_3[\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}(\text{Cr}_2^{\text{VI}}\text{O}_7)_3]$, of ethereal blue perchromate prepared in presence of 5-sulphosalicylic acid, reported earlier⁶⁻⁷, estimation of chromium has been carried out colorimetrically.

Experimental

Ethereal blue perchromate was prepared in the presence of 5-sulphosalicylic acid and then it was decomposed in 25 ml of double distilled water in the usual way^{3,6}. As per recommended procedure⁸ an aliquot of the water decomposition product (dichromate) was treated with *s*-diphenylcarbazide solution

and within 5 mins a violet coloured Cr(VI) complex was obtained. Next, the other aliquot of the test solution was oxidised to convert Cr(III) into Cr(VI) and then subjected to diphenylcarbazide treatment.

Transmittance (*T*) measurements of test and standard (dichromate) solutions after diphenylcarbazide treatment were recorded on "Aimil" photo colorimeter using 1 cm glass cell and a green filter having the transmission maximum at about 540 nm. Solvent blank containing approximate concentration of Cr(III) and sulphosalicylate ion was set up at 100% transmittance. Alternatively, to avoid the interference of these concentrations violet complex was extracted with carbontetrachloride. A standard calibration curve was obtained by plotting optical densities, $D = \log 1/T$, against varying volumes (conc. 50 μ gm/ml) of the standard solution which shows validity of Lambert-Beer's law.

Discussion

From the calibration curve the concentration of test solutions (unoxidised and oxidised) was ascertained. The increased concentration of oxidised test solution shows the presence of Cr(III) along with Cr(VI) in the decomposition product. The ratio between the concentration of Cr(VI) and oxidisable Cr(III) is 4.65 : 1.50 which comes nearly to the value 3 : 1 reported earlier⁶⁻⁷.

Thus ratio and inferences are in quite agreement with the formula $(\text{CrSu})_3[\text{Cr}(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3]$ for water decomposition product corresponding to the parent
 $\text{III} \quad \text{III} \quad \text{VI}$
 blue perchromate, $(\text{CrSu})_3[\text{Cr}(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})_3]$, where Su is bivalent sulphosalicylate ion.

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